

**THE EFFECT OF READING SKILL ON ACHIEVEMENT OF
VOCABULARY OF SECONDARY LEVEL STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

In this study researcher used Experimental Method for testing the achievement of vocabulary of Secondary School Students. There is purposive sampling method used and selected 20 students from 9th class. By using Single Group Design researcher give them proper treatment for achievement of vocabulary. It is proved that the treatment given by the researcher is significant.

Introduction:

India is multilingual country. There are various languages used by Indian people. So there is language diversity among them. English language taught in India as foreign language at school level. So it has more importance than other languages. Because English language is an International language. Language learning is a complex process, it requires the acquisition of various skills for the effective use of language. Among them reading skill is very important, If we survey school then we find various problems of reading among students. The students are unable to enjoy the beauty of language because they cannot use various strategy of reading skill.

“ Reading is the activity of looking at written or printed symbols and understanding them”

Reading is purposive activity. Because of reading we get information as well as knowledge of different things. It also develops the personality and we can express our opinion properly. It also develops vocabulary. Now a days we find various

problems among school within it reading is the major problem. From Primary to Secondary School students cannot read the vocabulary properly. Because they have lack of proper listening. So researcher tried to solve this problem through this study.

Statement of the Problem:

To study the effect of reading skill on achievement of vocabulary of secondary level students

Objectives of the Study:

- i) To study the accuracy and fluency of reading skill.
- ii) To understand the effectiveness of reading skill.
- iii) To obtain pre and post test score of vocabulary achievement of secondary students.
- iv) To compare the pre and post test score of reading skill.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference between the mean score of Pre and Post test of vocabulary achievement of secondary school students.

Sample:

For the present study researcher select IX class students of J.R. City High School, Dhule. Researcher used Purposive Sampling Method out of 73 students 20 selected as sample.

Research Method:

There are various methods of research. To see the effect of reading vocabulary researcher used Experimental Method for the study.

Research Design:

Research used Single Group Design i.e. Pre and Post test for the collection of data.

Pre Test (01) ----- X ----- Post Test (02)

Research Tools:

To collect the data from secondary school students researcher prepared the Achievement test based on Vocabulary for IX class students. It consists 20 marks.

Statistical Tools:

Researcher used statistical techniques like Mean, S.D.& t value for the accurate result of reading vocabulary of secondary school students.

Procedure:

Firstly researcher give the instruction about achievement test to students then researcher conduct Pre test (01). After that researcher give the treatment (X) to the students for two weeks of reading accurate vocabulary. While giving treatment about accurate reading of vocabulary, the researcher taught them how to read such words with the help of model recording. First of all such model recording of one word listen by the students, then such words were repeated by the students. In this way these twenty words were read by the students loudly. That time researcher gave them proper instructions about proper reading. Then researcher conduct Post test (02) and collect the data.

Analysis of Data:

Comparison of Pre and Post test Score

Test	N	M	S.D.	df	table t Value (0.05)	Calculated “t”	Level of Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Pre	20	13	0.40	19	2.09	13.18	Significant	Rejected
Post	20	15.9	0.33					

Interpretation:

The above statistical table shows that calculated “t” value (13.18) greater than table “t” value of (0.05) level i.e. 2.09 at 19 df. Calculated “t” value is significant. So Null Hypothesis is rejected. The calculated “t” value is significant at 0.05 level and the difference between Mean Score is $(15.9-13)=2.9$. It is because of Experimental treatment.

Findings:

With the above discussion we can conclude that if we give proper idea and guideline about reading then students can improve themselves. It is proved by the above discussion. The achievement of vocabulary reading increase among students because of systematic reading vocabulary.

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